

MATHEMATICAL MODELING AND FORECASTING OF THE SUPPLY OF ELECTRICITY TO THE NATIONAL ECONOMY OF THE COUNTRY

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The country's economy is inextricably linked with electricity supplies. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 27, 2019 No. PP-4249 "On the Strategy for Further Development and Reform of the Electric Power Complex of the Republic of Uzbekistan" states that "without ensuring the reliable operation of the electric power complex, it is impossible to increase the industrial potential of the country's industries and regions, stimulate the development of entrepreneurial activity, improve the well-being of the population and improve the quality of life".

In this regard, it is relevant to develop a mathematical model of the dynamics of electricity supply in the Republic of Uzbekistan, its analysis and preparation of forecasts for future periods.

After the adoption of the Action Strategy in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017, special attention was paid to electricity supply.

To ensure the implementation of the tasks set in it, large-scale reforms are being carried out. From this point of view, it is advisable to separately analyze the economic changes that occurred in the Republic of Uzbekistan before and after 2017 [1-4].

Electricity supply in regions and countries of the world, indicators and analytical materials based on them are presented in [5-8].

Based on data from the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the mathematical model of the dynamics of electricity supply in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2010-2023 is as follows:

$$y = 142,85t^2 + 57,747t + 50908, \quad R^2 = 0,988 \quad (1)$$

The value of this mathematical model's fit to the data is $R^2 = 0.988$, which indicates that the mathematical model has a very high level of reliability.

If we analyze these indicators separately for the periods up to and after 2017, we obtain the following models:

$$y = 1130,1t + 49466, \quad R^2 = 0,9838 \quad (2)$$

$$y = 3253,9t + 56394, \quad R^2 = 0,9681 \quad (3)$$

From the analysis, it can be seen that the growth rate in 2016 compared to 2010 was 13.38%, and in 2023 the growth rate compared to 2016 was 29.31%, and compared to 2010 it was 53.17%, that is, significant growth was achieved after 2017.

The results of the analysis showed that during periods of fundamental changes in the economy, it is advisable to separately analyze the periods before and after the fundamental changes, as the author previously suggested, and on their basis create mathematical models and draw conclusions.

In joint articles [4-7], the indicators of electricity supply of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2005-2020, and before and after 2017, were analyzed. According to them, the goal set for 2030 cannot be achieved with the first use of the methodology and recommendations for its achievement

are given. The results of the analysis show that the radical changes in the energy system have yielded results.

The growth rate of the volume of electricity supply in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2016 compared to 2010 was 13.38%, in 2023 compared to 2016 - 29.31%, and compared to 2010 - 53.17%, that is, significant growth was achieved after 2017.

The article showed that if electricity supply is implemented through the model (3) presented, the goal set in the "Concept of Electricity Supply of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030", namely the plan to increase electricity supply to 120.8 billion kWh in 2030, can be increased (to 124.7 billion kWh) [8].

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